

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

CYCLIC ALGORITHM FOR BUILDING THE ODD ORDER MAGIC SQUARE

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Abstract

This is another linear algorithm with difficulty of $O(n^2)$ to build the magic square of odd order. In order to fill cells I use two “periodic operations”: “periodic addition” and “periodic subtraction”.

Keywords: Magic square, cyclic algorithm, periodic operations

History of magic square

The magic square is a square, where we place all numbers from 1 to n^2 in $n \times n$ square, where sum of elements in all rows, columns and two diagonals is a constant value. This square is historically interested many mathematicians. The 3, 4, 5 and more orders of such magic square was built by empiric way in different periods of the history. However, we interested on building of any n order magic square.

Building problem of n order magic square is investigating in three different cases. n is an odd number, n is dividing to 4 and n is even but not dividing to 4. The simplest and unexceptional case is building of odd order magic square. I already encountered the algorithm for odd order and $4k$ (n is multiple of 4) order magic squares. However, I did not see an algorithm for even order where n is not a multiple of 4. Recently, I encountered the algorithm of construction of any n -order square and even cube by Professor Askar Ali Abiyev. Indeed this algorithm was valid for any natural number of n . When I meet this professor after our conversation all night I was thinking around this magic square. As a result, I built my own algorithm that I'll explain below. This algorithm is valid only for odd order magic square.

Cyclic algorithm

I named this algorithm “cyclic” because I use only two (outer and inner) cycles and use two “periodic operations” (or “cyclic operations”). These operations will be explained below.

There are n^2 numbers in n -order square. If we consider them as arithmetic progression, we must place them in cells in such order, that their sum in any direction will be the constant value. We can easily find this constant value.

The formula for sum of elements of arithmetic progression is $S = \frac{n^2(n^2+1)}{2}$. It is the sum of all elements that fill entire square. Because any row and any column elements sum is a constant value, this value must be $\frac{S}{n}$. Say this value is $M = \frac{n(n^2+1)}{2}$.

Let's define two “periodic operations” before starting the explanation of the main algorithm. One of them is addition based on n^2 (we mark it by \oplus sign), other operation is subtraction based on n^2 (we mark it by \ominus sign).

If $a, b \in \{1, \dots, n^2\}$ and $a \neq b$, then

$$a \oplus b = \begin{cases} a + b, & \text{if } a + b \leq n \\ a + b - n^2, & \text{if } a + b > n \end{cases} \quad a \ominus b = \begin{cases} a - b, & \text{if } a - b > 0 \\ a - b + n^2, & \text{if } a - b < 0 \end{cases}$$

Because $a \neq b$ we never obtain zero (0) during subtraction operation. As we see the domain of definition and range of values are $\{1, \dots, n^2\}$. We can write the above-defined operations in way that is more compact:

$$a \oplus b = (a + b - 1) \% n^2 + 1 \quad a \ominus b = (a - b + n^2) \% n^2$$

where $\%$ is an operation of remainder from division.

Now I will build the magic square with the aid of these periodic operations. First of all I will explain the algorithm for case of $n = 5$, and after, will show the common case. For the 5-order square, any row, column and both diagonal values sum are $M = \frac{5(5^2+1)}{2} = 65$.

Step 1.

I place the number of 13 in the central point of square. Because the central point is the center of mass of our square, I place there the central member of an arithmetic progression.

Moving from center to the left square in the same row, I subtract 4 from the previous cell's value and write to the new cell, i.e. to the left cell from 13 I write $13 \ominus 4 = 9$, to the leftmost cell I write $9 \ominus 4 = 5$. Then moving from center to the right cell of the same row I add 4 to the previous cell's value and write to the new cell, i.e. to the right cell from 13 I write $13 \oplus 4 = 17$, to the rightmost cell I write $17 \oplus 4 = 21$. So I filled all central row.

Now I fill the vertical row passing through the center. I add 6 to the central element and write to the upper cell. For the topmost cell I add 6 to the previous cell's value and write here, i.e. $13 \oplus 6 = 19$ and $19 \oplus 6 = 25$. By the same way I go down and fill the cells of this column below to the central cell. Every time I subtract 6 from the previous value, i.e. $13 \ominus 6 = 7$ and $7 \ominus 6 = 1$. So I placed the numbers in ascending order from left to right and from down to up. I finished the 1-st step of algorithm. In the picture below the central lines shown in green color.

		25		
		19		
5	9	13	17	21
		7		
		1		

18	16	25	4	8
6	15	19	23	2
5	9	13	17	21
24	3	7	11	20
18	22	1	10	14

Step 2.

As a result of previous step the square is divided into 4 small squares. Now I'll fill left upper and down squares in parallel. For this reason starting from cell neighboring to the center I go down and subtract 6 every time from upper square's value. $9 \ominus 6 = 3$, $3 \ominus 6 = 22$. Let me mention one point here. I move one step to the left from center in descending direction and falling down also in descending direction. Therefore I go down one step more in descending direction, i.e. I also calculate $22 \ominus 6 = 16$. But I have no more cells here. Therefore, I write this value to the topmost cell of this column. Descending direction is shown in yellow color in the below picture.

Now I go up starting from the cell containing the value 9. I write the value $9 \oplus 6 = 15$ to this upper cell. So I finished the work with this column. Ascending direction is shown in red color in the below picture.

The leftmost column also filling by the same rule. $5 \oplus 6 = 24$, $24 \ominus 6 = 18$. Now I go 2 steps left from the center. Therefore, I must go down by 2 "extra steps". After filling two columns below I write the remaining two values to the upper cells of this column. $18 \oplus 6 = 12$, $12 \oplus 6 = 6$.

18	16	25		
6	15	19		
5	9	13	17	21
24	3	7		
18	22	1		

Step 3.

I fill the right squares by the same way. Now I move in ascending order by horizontal line and fill the column also in ascending order. Therefore, I do an "extra step" in ascending order. There is a value 17 in the next cell from center. I add 6 to this value, then add 6 to the obtained value and fill the above cells correspondingly. $17 \oplus 6 = 23$, $23 \oplus 6 = 4$. But we have no cell above to write the value obtained from "extra step". Therefore I write this value ($4 \oplus 6 = 10$) to the last cell of this column. Then I fill the cell below 17. Because I go in descending direction I write $17 \ominus 6 = 11$ to this cell.

Now I fill the rightmost column. I start from the value 21 and add 6 to this value: $21 \oplus 6 = 2$, $2 \oplus 6 = 8$. As I move in ascending direction by the central row and fill the cells vertically in ascending order and I am far from the center by 2 steps, I must do 2 "extra steps". Therefore, I fill all the elements of this column by adding 6 to every previous cell. $8 \oplus 6 = 14$, $14 \oplus 6 = 20$. I write these values to the below cells of the rightmost column.

So I built the magic square of 5×5 . You can check that sum of every row, every column and two diagonal elements is 65.

Let me give you the simple way to remember this algorithm. Consider the central row and column as coordinate axes of Cartesian system. First of all we moved by axis x in descending order. If we move by axis y also in descending order it means we are moving in descending order by both axis. You can consider it as our "privilege". Therefore we do an extra step in descending direction. The count of extra steps is defined by how far we are from the center.

When we move in ascending order by the axis y we must pay a "penalty" because we move in descending order by x axis but in ascending order by y axis. Therefore we do less steps in ascending direction. The farther we are from the center, the fewer steps we take.

The reverse of this case is happening when we fill the right squares. First we go in ascending order by x and y axis. Therefore we have a "privilege" in this direction and "ascending rule" takes place. The farther we are from the center, the more steps we take in positive (ascending) direction. When we go in descending order by y axis we are breaking the "ascending rule" and pay "penalty" equal to the distance from the center.

Common case of the cyclic algorithm

Now I'll try to explain this algorithm for any odd value of n .

Step 1.

Place in the center of the square the number $\frac{n^2+1}{2}$. As I mentioned above it is the center of mass of our square, I place here the central member of our arithmetic progression. Then I fill the elements of row and column that go through the center. Note that there is no need to use circular operations when calculating the central row and column elements, since the result never exceeds the set $\{1, \dots, n^2\}$. Therefore below I wrote "+" and "-" instead of " \oplus " and " \ominus "

Starting from center and going to the left I subtract $n - 1$ from previous cell's value and write to the cell. So the next elements will be equal to:

$$\frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - (n - 1) = \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2}$$

$$\frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - 2(n - 1) = \frac{n^2 - 4n + 5}{2}$$

$$\dots$$

$$\frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - \frac{n - 1}{2}(n - 1) = \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - \frac{n^2 - 2n + 1}{2}$$

$$= n$$

As steps count is $\frac{n-1}{2}$, I obtain n for the leftmost column.

For the right cells of the central row I add $n - 1$ to the previous cell's value:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + (n - 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \\ \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + 2(n - 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 4n - 3}{2} \\ &\dots \\ \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + \frac{n - 1}{2}(n - 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + \frac{n^2 - 2n + 1}{2} \\ &= n^2 - n + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Then I fill the below part of the central column. For this purpose I subtract $n + 1$ from previous cell's value:

$$\frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - (n + 1) = \frac{n^2 - 2n - 1}{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - 2(n + 1) &= \frac{n^2 - 4n - 3}{2} \\ &\dots \\ \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - \frac{n - 1}{2}(n + 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} - \frac{n^2 - 1}{2} = 1 \end{aligned}$$

By the same way for above part of the central column, I add $n + 1$ to the previous cell's value.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + (n + 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 2n + 3}{2} \\ \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + 2(n + 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 4n + 5}{2} \\ &\dots \\ \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + \frac{n - 1}{2}(n + 1) &= \frac{n^2 + 1}{2} + \frac{n^2 - 1}{2} = n^2 \end{aligned}$$

As result I obtain the below picture.

				n^2				
				...				
				$\frac{n^2 + 4n + 5}{2}$				
				$\frac{n^2 + 2n + 3}{2}$				
n	...	$\frac{n^2 - 4n + 5}{2}$	$\frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2}$	$\frac{n^2 + 1}{2}$	$\frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2}$	$\frac{n^2 + 4n - 3}{2}$...	$n^2 - n + 1$
				$\frac{n^2 - 2n - 1}{2}$				
				$\frac{n^2 - 4n - 3}{2}$				
				...				
				1				

Step 2.

Starting from the left element of center and going down every time me "periodically subtract" $n + 1$ from the previous cell.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \ominus (n + 1) \\ \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \ominus 2(n + 1) \\ \dots \\ \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \ominus \frac{n - 1}{2}(n + 1) \end{aligned}$$

When I reach to the end of column, I write an "extra" element to the first cell of this column.

$$\frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \ominus \frac{n + 1}{2}(n + 1)$$

I fill the remaining cells of this column by "periodic addition" operation.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \oplus (n + 1) \\ \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \oplus 2(n + 1) \\ \dots \\ \frac{n^2 - 2n + 3}{2} \oplus \frac{n - 3}{2}(n + 1) \end{aligned}$$

As you see, I made one-step less in this direction. It is the "penalty" mechanism that I mentioned before.

All left columns are filled by the same manner. Every time when I switch to the next left column, I make addition steps in descending direction and less steps in ascending direction. As for from center as more

steps in descending direction and as less steps in ascending direction.

Step 3.

Starting from the right element of center and going up every time I "periodically add" $n + 1$ to the previous cell.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \oplus (n + 1) \\ \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \oplus 2(n + 1) \\ \dots \\ \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \oplus \frac{n - 1}{2}(n + 1) \end{aligned}$$

When I reach to the first element of column, I write an "extra" element to the last cell of this column.

$$\frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \oplus \frac{n + 1}{2}(n + 1)$$

I fill the remaining cells of this column by "periodic subtraction" operation.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \ominus (n + 1) \\ \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \ominus 2(n + 1) \\ \dots \\ \frac{n^2 + 2n - 1}{2} \ominus \frac{n - 3}{2}(n + 1) \end{aligned}$$

As you noticed, I made one extra step in ascending direction and one less step in descending direction. It is the "privilege" and "penalty" mechanism correspondingly.

By the same way, I fill all the right columns. This time as far I go from the center as extra steps I make in ascending direction and as less steps I make in descending direction. In the rightmost column remains only ascending direction.

I would like to mention one fact that changing the horizontal and vertical steps does not change the result. Therefore, we can take $n + 1$ as a step of x axis and $n - 1$ as a step of y axis.

Because of large formulas, I did not write them into following picture. I painted the central row and column in green color, positive (ascending) directions in red color and negative (descending) directions in yellow color.

References:

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